

THE EFFICACY OF GAME-BASED APPLICATION ON PUPILS WITH DYSCALCULIA IN NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper presents the efficacy of game-based application on mathematics basic skills' mastery of pupils with dyscalculia in primary schools in north-east Nigeria. Two objectives and two research hypotheses were formulated for the study. The researchers made use of an experimental research design; the pre-test posttest control group design. The study was conducted in ten randomly selected (10) primary School from six (6) state in north-east zone where the researchers purposively sampled eighty pupils (80) with mathematics difficulties. Test was concurrently administered to all the pupils at their respective schools by employed trained research assistants for the first time (pre-test) then intervention followed using game-based app for five (5) schools selected as experimental group and regular teaching strategies used for the remaining five (5) schools selected as control group all for the period of thirty (30) minutes each per three (3) days over the length of eight (8) weeks after which the researchers re-administered the same tests (posttest). Scores were collated and fed into the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). The t-test for dependent samples was used to test the research hypothesis which shown that, the pre-test means scores of both experimental and control group insignificantly differ shows that $t(78) = 0.74, p > 0.05$. Based on this it could be deduced that both the groups are equivalent in terms of performance before receiving any form of treatment. The posttest mean scores on the other hand indicated that pupils in the experimental group was found to have risen $\bar{X} = 84.27$, while that of the control group was $\bar{X} = 76.64$. It was therefore observed that the result of the experimental group is higher than that of the control group and independent sample t-test was ran to ascertain whether the different observed was statistically significant. With the statistic $t(78) = 4.56, p < 0.05$, the two groups were observed to significantly differ in favor of the experimental group, this has significantly shown that game-based app is effective in remediation of pupils with dyscalculia in north-eastern Nigeria.

Keywords: Efficacy, Game Based Application, Dyscalculia,

Introduction

Basic numeracy is a fundamental skill in modern society. With basic numeracy one can handle money and change fairly easily. People with dyscalculia are often able to get by, but do so at a distinct disadvantage. Mathematics is all about identifying patterns, recognizing structures and investigating the logical consequences of hypotheses. These skills are necessary before anything else when making a decision, passing a judgment, using a computer or reading the news. These were considered as reasons that mathematics as a subject stand compulsory at lower school level. Recent research on mathematics education shows that students face difficulty in understanding mathematical concepts and to develop logical thinking and strategy to deal with mathematics problems. It is required from teachers to implement teaching which will result in the development of critical mathematical thinking by students, rather than a sterile assimilation of mathematical formulas. In an attempt to analyse what makes it difficult to learn mathematical concepts and skills, it could considers straightly involved

attention problems, cognitive-processing problems, auditory problems, memory problems and metacognitive deficits (Drigas, 2014).

Smedt, Janssen, Bouwens, Verschaffel, Boets and Ghesquiere (2009) stated that children with mathematical disabilities are usually linked to poor working memory. Working memory seems to be directly related to students' mathematics achievement, as well as its two subsystems, the phonological loop and the visuospatial sketchpad which are used for passive information storage. Taura (2016) cited Jordan and Hanich, (2003) that children with mathematics disorder (MD) tend to be slower and less accurate in the execution and retrieval strategies and use less efficient counting procedures than their typically achieving peers when computing the correct result of a given problem. Abba, Hafsat, Bashir and Auwal (2007) stated that learning materials that could be employed in their teaching include picture cards, words on plastic and cubes, dominoes, abacus, flash cards, calculators, bottle tops, tape recorders, plastic numbers, overhead projectors, picture cards, small blocks, comic strips, video, filmstrips viewer and so forth.

Statement of the Problem

It is an obvious fact that some students with learning disabilities experience difficulty with numeracy or counting ability and probably could be considered dyscalculic. The problem of non-application of reasonable accommodations for individuals with mathematics disabilities can create a setback in the achievement and successes of educational process in Nigeria. Without finding the most beneficial support for numeracy skills mastery which could be attained through the practice of math game-based application teaching strategy, learning tends to slowdown. Therefore, this study seeks to suggest the intervention that will encourage practice through low-stress opportunities for young students' and teenagers' mathematic development (Wiggins & McTigne, 2005).

Purpose of the Study

The objective of the study is to find out:

1. The significant pre-test difference between the experimental and control group of pupils with dyscalculia remediated through game-based applications and the control group remediated through other regular teaching strategies;
2. The significant post-test difference between the experimental and control group of pupils with dyscalculia remediated through game-based applications and the control group remediated through other regular teaching strategies;

Research Hypotheses

The study seeks to test the following null hypotheses:

H₀₁ there is no significant pre-test difference in the mean scores between experimental and control group in mathematics Game-based application on numeracy mastery skills of the pupils with Dyscalculia in North-East, Nigeria.

H₀₂ there is no significant post-test difference in the mean scores between experimental and control group in mathematics Game-based application on numeracy mastery skills of the pupils with Dyscalculia in North-East, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This study is expected to educate all stake-holders on the positive role of game-based application as a learning tool in the teaching and learning process for all learning-disabled middle-grade School Students. It will provide relevant information on the impact of game-based application in teaching students with dyscalculia among middle-grade level students. This will help in reminding education planners, teachers, and administrators to ensure that game-based application is adequately mastered and practiced as teaching strategy by mathematics teachers in the country.

Literature Review

Dyscalculia- a learning disability that negatively affects the normal development of mathematics skill. A difficulty in understanding numbers, learning how to manipulate numbers, performing mathematical calculations and learning facts in mathematics

Types of Dyscalculia

According to the website *Dyslexia in Ireland, (2020)*, dyscalculia can be broken down into the following subtypes:

1. **Quantitative dyscalculia;** - a deficit in the skills of counting and calculating.
2. **Qualitative dyscalculia;** - a result of difficulties in comprehension of instructions or the failure to master the skills required for an operation. When a child has not mastered the memorization of number facts, he cannot benefit from this stored “verbalizable information about numbers” that is used with prior associations to solve problems involving addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, and square roots.
3. **Intermediate dyscalculia** involves the inability to operate with symbols, or numbers.
4. **Verbal dyscalculia**, which refers to problems in naming the amount of things.
5. **Practognostic dyscalculia**, which refers to problems in manipulating things mathematically — for example, comparing objects to determine which is larger.
6. **Lexical dyscalculia**, which refers to problems in reading mathematical symbols, including operation signs (+, −) and numerals.
7. **Graphical dyscalculia**, which refers to problems in writing mathematical symbols and numerals.
8. **Ideognostical dyscalculia**, which refers to problems in understanding mathematical concepts and relationships.
9. **Operational Dyscalculia**, which refers to problems in performing arithmetic operations.

Theoretical Framework

Classical Conditioning Theory of Learning by Ivan P. Pavlov

According to this theory, learning is in formation of conditioned reflexes or acquisition of involuntary anticipatory adjustment or a habit formation so that behaviour may become automatic. In this theory, (Pavlov 1897) a Russian psychologist, experimented on dogs to study how stimuli and responses are associated. He established a conditioned response of salvation in a dog. In his experiment, he took a dog, kept him in a room and repeatedly gave ringing of a bell as a stimulus, soon followed by food which led to salvation. Bell and food were presented in a sequence over a number of times (seven days) and at every trial there was the bell. A stage reached when ringing of the bell led to normal salvation even when there was no food supplied. It could be deduced that the stimulus (bell) followed by food, led to response. The relevance of this theory could be seen in the area of development of attitude in children. Conditioning may help a child in breaking negative

attitude and promoting positive one. Good and bad habit may be developed in children through method of conditioning. Proper habit can be formed by providing education of positive behaviour.

This research work builds on the aforementioned theory in the sense that the game-based applications serve as stimuli whereas Girl-Childs' mathematical ability serve as response in which case the stimuli is expected to elicit positive response.

Empirical Studies

Boot, Kramer, Simons, Fabiani & Gratton in 2008 conducted a similar research work on the effects of video game playing on attention, memory, and executive control using cross-sectional research design. They examined the effects of video game playing, on attention, memory and executive control. Twenty-one pupils, eleven expert video game players, in games such as Halo, Grand Theft Auto and Unreal Tournament, and ten non-video-game players participated in their study. The researchers used visual and attentional tasks, short memory tasks and executive control and reasoning tasks to find out whether there are differences between people who play video games frequently and those who don't. The results showed that video game experts outbalanced non-video-gamers in most tasks. The studies finding showed that, video game training seems to be a promising way for entertaining perceptual, attentional and cognitive abilities improvement.

In another study of a topic, 'game-based app. And mathematics skills' through quasi-experimental design conducted by Dye, Green and Bavelier in 2009 after which they suggested that action video games could develop attention skills. A total of 131 students participated in their study, 56 video games players and 75 non-video games players. All participants were asked to take the Attentional Network Test (ANT) in order to measure their attention skills. Analysis of the tests showed a finding that playing action video games speeded processing of visual information and improved attention skills of the players. Furthermore, there was no significant difference between gamers and non-gamers on how they use a valid spatial cue to allocate their attention'.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopts experimental design. The experimental design involved the pretest-posttest control group design that involves randomized assignment of subjects to two groups viz, experimental and control groups. Participants in each group will receive a pretest before being exposed to the intervention and a posttest after the intervention (Bottge, 1999).

Sample and Selection Procedure

The population of this study covered eighty (80) primary six pupils of Yagana Lawal Primary School Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The sample of the study was derived from the population of the study through purposive sampling technique. The findings of the study, therefore, will be generalized to all the middle grade learning institutions in North-East, Nigeria.

Data Collection Instruments

The instruments to be used for data gathering in this research was test and checklist. The test for this study was researchers' developed test for identifying pupils with difficulty on basic early beginner's numeracy. The checklist was adopted by the researchers for the purpose of this study.

Results

In this study, both pre-test and post-test were administered to both the experimental group and control group and the results are shown in the following tables.

Hypothesis One: there is no significant pre-test difference in the mean scores between experimental and control group in mathematics Game-based application on numeracy mastery skills of the pupils with Dyscalculia in North-East, Nigeria.

Table 1: Result of the pre-test scores of the experimental and control group

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Tcal	<i>p</i>	Decision
Experimental	40	45.83	10.51			
Control	40	44.25	9.84	0.74	0.46	Not Significant

In the above table, the result shows that there was no significant difference between the experimental and control groups. And independent sample T-test was run and the statistics shows that $t(78) = 0.74, p > 0.05$. Based on this it could be deduced that both the groups are equivalent in terms of performance before receiving any form of treatment.

Hypothesis Two: there is no significant post-test difference in the mean scores between experimental and control group in mathematics Game-based application on numeracy mastery skills of the pupils with Dyscalculia in North-East, Nigeria.

Table 2: Result of the post-test scores of the experimental and control group

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Tcal	<i>p</i>	Decision
Experimental	40	84.27	6.24			
Control	40	76.64	6.46	4.56	0.00	Significant

After treatment, the means scores of the pupils in the experimental group was found to have risen $\bar{X} = 84.27$, while that of the control group was $\bar{X} = 76.64$. It was therefore observed that the result of the experimental group is higher than that of the control group and independent sample t-test was ran to ascertain whether the different observed was statistically significant. With the statistic $t(78) = 4.56, p < 0.05$, the two groups were observed to significantly differ in favour of the experimental group, this has significantly shown that game-based application are effective in remediation of pupils with dyscalculia in North-East.

Summary and Discussion of Findings

This study found that at pre-test level, there was no significant difference between experimental and control group that was statistically observed through their mean standard deviation and the t-test for independent samples. It is in line with the works of Dye, Green and Bavelier (2009). It was also found that there was statistically significant difference at post-test level between experimental and control group. This has with the findings of Boot, Kramer, Simons, Fabiani and Gratton (2008).

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study it is recommended that game-based applications should be adopted for use at local, state and federal levels for teaching especially early graders suffering from dyscalculia.

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